

Original Research Report

Effect of Parenting Styles on Emotional Adjustment of Children in Secondary School in Nnewi South of Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study looked into how parenting styles affected secondary school-aged children's emotional adjustment. It specifically referred to the senior and junior secondary schools in the Anambra state's Nnewi South LGA. Based on pertinent literature, two research questions were developed. The various parenting philosophies, as well as self-concept and emotional adjustment, were examined. Senior and junior secondary school students that responded to the survey. Six secondary schools were sampled, and the results were utilized to identify the responders. The questionnaires used as the investigation's tool received responses from 180 boys and girls. The survey asks for personal information like gender and details on parenting practices and emotional adjustment. The study's results also showed that there is only a tenuous connection between parental parenting practices and secondary school students' emotional adjustment. This indicates that changes in parenting practices are not connected to changes in the emotional adjustment of teenagers. Additionally, there is no statistically significant relationship between parenting styles and secondary school children's emotional adjustment. The study's recommendations for parents include making sure that the parenting style they employ for their youngsters will aid in the development of healthy emotional adjustment and allowing the school counselor to start a program that will assist students in creating positive emotional self-concept.

Keywords: Emotional Adjustment, Parents, Parenting Style, Secondary School, Students

1. Introduction

Children's emotional development is greatly influenced by parents. The way a kid experiences emotion may be influenced by both indirect and direct processes of emotional socialization. Parenting style should be taken into account when analyzing parental socialization since it "reflects the constellation of attitudes that are conveyed to the kid and generate an emotional milieu in which parent's conduct are displayed. Researchers have made an effort to conceptualize and operationalize parenting styles into useful categories or dimensions, such authoritative, authoritarian, permissive parenting, and negligent parenting styles, in order to comprehend how parents impact their children (Nwogu, 2016). Parenting with authoritative style demonstrates strong control and strong attentiveness. Higher degrees of effortful control and self-regulation have been linked to this parenting approach (Goering & Mrug, 2021). Authoritarian parenting, on the other hand, exhibits greater control and less warmth. They are demanding and insensitive to a child's emotional needs (Schneider & Schenck-Fontaine, 2022). High degrees of warmth and low levels of control are characteristics of permissive parenting (Wischerth, Mulvaney, Brackett & Perkins, 2016). In a parenting approach known as negligent parenting, parents fail to attend to their adolescent child's needs or wants beyond the bare necessities of food, clothes, and shelter.

Adolescence is a time of transitional physical and psychological growth that typically occurs between puberty and adulthood. Adolescence is also frequently a period of enthusiasm and problems, making it a complex time. Adolescents do, in fact, have various levels of self-esteem and responses to their environment (Ahunovna, 2021). Some are really welcoming, while others are highly hostile and confrontational. Some of these teenagers have been seen to exhibit maladaptive behaviors and interpersonal interactions with other teenagers and adults in the community. Some of these teenagers who struggle with emotional stability are unable to adapt, cope, or emotionally mature. Parenting techniques are also the behavioral tactics parents use to socialize their youngsters. Practices like emotional support have been demonstrated to be favorably connected with emotional adjustment when used in the context of learning activities.

The state or process of personally accepting and adapting to one's circumstances, which may include altering attitudes and expressing emotions that are acceptable for a particular context, is known as emotional adjustment. In the face of both internal and external pressures, it is the preservation of emotional balance. Cognitive mechanisms of acceptance and adaption help with this. Emotional adjustment is a crucial endeavor because, whereas maladjustment results in aberrant conduct, adjustment during emotions leads to normal behavior. The various parenting philosophies employed by a parent and a kid have an impact on emotional adjustment (Van-Lissa & Keizer, 2020). The way a parent interacts with their child will affect how that youngster will be as an adult. According to Bandura's social learning theory, kids observe, pick up on, and imitate the actions they see around them every day. These actions are observed and assessed depending on the indirect or direct modeling provided by their parents.

The need for this study stems from the fact that parenting styles can have an impact on teenage self-perception and social emotional development. In contrast to emotional adjustment, which is the capability to perform effectively under pressure, psychological intelligence is the capacity to work through issues using knowledge and experience while overcoming sentiments and emotions. These parenting techniques have a significant impact on how a person perceives themselves, their view of their physical, social, and psychological aspirations, and their emotional adjustment to the culture in which they live. Therefore, it is crucial to research various parenting philosophies and determine how

they influence a child's emotional adjustment to society.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Parenting is the collection of techniques used by parents to govern their kids' behavior, which can be impacted by a variety of elements such as socioeconomic structures, cultural variations, individual traits, and psychological elements. Today's parents frequently pay insufficient attention to their children's education and growth. Furthermore, some of these parents that do so use unsuitable parenting techniques, while others don't spend enough time with their children. These students thus suffer from inadequate parental guidance in terms of their emotional, intellectual, physical, and moral development. Students who lack mental stability and self-assurance eventually turn into annoyances and burdens to themselves, their families, and others around them. In actuality, a lot of students who currently have extremely poor self-esteem do so as a result of their parents' chosen parenting approach. Low self-esteem in students makes them less intrinsically motivated to achieve in many endeavors in life. Additionally, it has been shown that students with poor self-esteem are more likely to join covert cults as a means of self-defense and compensating for their lack of confidence.

The researcher has seen that secondary school students in the Nnewi South of Anambra State engage in a variety of immoral behaviors, including cultism, low self-esteem, substance abuse, rape, abduction, and murder as well as examination fraud, prostitution, and adolescent pregnancy, to name a few. Both the researcher and the school administration are now concerned about this. Although there are other institutions for socialization, the impact of parental style on secondary school kids' emotional development remains to be seen.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

This study's overarching goal is to determine how parenting styles affect secondary school students in Anambra state's Nnewi South LGA's emotional adjustment. The study specifically aimed to ascertain:

- (a) The parenting styles of secondary school student's parent in Nnewi South LGA of Anambra state.
- (b) How parenting styles impacts on emotional adjustment of children in secondary school.

1.3. Research Questions

The investigation was based on the following research question.

- (a) What are the parenting styles of secondary school student's parent in Nnewi South LGA of Anambra state?
- (b) Do parenting styles affect the emotional adjustment of the secondary school students?

1.4. Significance of the Study

This kind of research will advance our understanding of parenting practices and emotional development. This work will also be helpful to individuals who seek to do data analysis on parenting practices and teenage mental health. Additionally, knowing how their actions affect their kids can help parents create programs that will strengthen their bonds with their adolescent children. The study will also assist professionals, such as psychologists, in understanding how social support, behavior modification, and teenage emotions all contribute to successful child parenting.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The research design for the study was a descriptive survey. The survey technique was used to do this, and the questionnaire was used to obtain the quantitative data. Surveys are very valuable in the fields of social and behavioral science, as well as other fields that examine human behavior, hence they were thought to be the most appropriate method for this study.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The faculty research ethics review committee gave its approval to the project. The proper distribution of study-related information, consent and assent forms was made. The author received permission from the secondary school institutions to perform the research. Additionally, the consent of the participants' parents was requested and authorized by the corresponding secondary school administrators. The attendees also expressed their agreement. The researcher also conformed with the ethical standards for research involving human subjects.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was carried out at secondary schools in the Anambra state's Nnewi South LGA. Only junior and senior secondary school students in Anambra state's Nnewi South LGA served as the respondents for the study. This is due to the researcher's acquaintance with the local geography and surroundings.

2.3. Population and Sample

All the eighteen (18) public junior/senior secondary schools in the Nnewi South LGA of the state of Anambra made up the research population. There are 45,795 students in senior secondary schools (PPSSC, 2017). The researcher chose two (2) schools from each of the six (6) Area Councils located in the Nnewi South LGA of the Anambra state using a stratified random selection approach. Additionally, respondents from each of the chosen schools were chosen using a proportional stratified selection. The researcher gathered data from 6 schools since a typical class is anticipated to contain 40 students. The data was gathered from 180 students because the classes had a little bit more than forty student. The researcher selected three boys' schools and three girls' schools using basic random selection. Simple random sampling was used to choose the necessary stream when there are more than two streams in a school.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A questionnaire was employed by the researcher to gather data from the students. The questionnaire was designed to determine the various parenting approaches adopted by parents and how these approaches impact children's emotional adjustment. This was an adopted questionnaire named Parenting Style and Emotional adjustment Questionnaire (PSEDQ). The questionnaire has three sections (A, B & C). Section A contains the personal data such as gender (Male/Female); section B contains relevant information regarding parenting style adopted from Gafoor and Jurukkan (2014), the section contained twenty (20) items on a four point scale of 1 = Almost Never True; 2 = Rarely True; 3 = Sometimes True; 4 = Almost Always True; Similarly, section C contains relevant information regarding emotional adjustment adopted from Alegre (2008), the section contained twenty (20) items on a four point scale of 1= Not true of me; 2 = Sometimes true of me; 3 = Often true of me; 4 = Very true of me.

The instrument was validated by two specialists, one from Educational Psychology and the other from Home Economics Education. The changes from the validations were implemented, and the instrument was deemed suitable for the research. The instrument was trial-tested with 10 respondents

who were not involved in the main study. They were given copies of the questionnaire to complete, and these were collected immediately. The questionnaire's components were reshuffled and rearranged before being given to the same group of respondents 2 weeks later. The Cronbach's Alpha estimation technique was used to gather and test them, yielding a score of 0.88. This shows that the instrument is reliable.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Parents of every kid attending one of the participating schools received letters outlining the study and seeking their consent to participate. The student assent form, which outlines the study's objectives and the voluntariness of participation as well as the fact that participating students will get a pencil in exchange for their involvement, was also sent to students whose parents had returned the parental agreement form. Students were only included if they also consented to participating. After receiving permission from the instructors and parents, the researcher carried out the survey while classes were in session at the school. With the assistance of two research assistants, the researcher gathered the study's data. 180 questionnaires In total were distributed and collected with a 100% response rate. The students completed all of the questions in around 50 minutes.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

In order to organize, code, and analyze the acquired data, frequency tables, percentages, and cross-tabulation were used. Using the computer tool Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), data were processed. Demographic characteristics were described using descriptive statistics (gender). Bivariate correlational analyses were utilized to explore links between parenting styles and emotional adjustment. The utilized p value threshold was 0.05. The data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlations since the variables were continuous and had a linear relationship (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2010). The data were interpreted, and conclusions were taken.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Respondents characteristics:* Table 1 demonstrates that a sample of 180 secondary school students in the Nnewi South LGA of the state of Anambra completed the questionnaire. 180 students completed the questionnaire, with 60 of them being male (33.33% of the sample), and 120 being female (66.67% of the sample).

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	33.33%
Female	120	66.67%
TOTAL	180	100%

3.2. *Research question one:* What are the parenting styles of secondary school student's parent in Nnewi South LGA of Anambra State?

Table 2: Parenting styles of secondary school student's parent in Nnewi South LGA of Anambra State

S/N	ITEMS	ANT	RT	ST	AAT	Mean	Std Dev
Authoritative Parenting							
1	Strong and reliable in their control.	15 (8.33%)	20 (11.11%)	65 (36.11%)	80 (44.44%)	2.20	0.93
2	Parents should keep an eye on their children'	35 (19.44%)	15 (8.33%)	45 (25%)	85 (47.22%)	2.40	1.15

	behavior and set clear expectations for it.						
3	Parents encourage their kids to seek objectives that appear beyond their age.	15 (8.33%)	25 (13.88%)	35 (19.44%)	105 (58.33%)	2.07	0.99
4	Promote independence in children.	15 (8.33%)	20 (11.11%)	10 (5.56%)	135 (75%)	1.83	0.99
5	Encourage independence.	95 (52.78%)	25 (13.89%)	25 (13.88%)	35 (19.44%)	3.60	1.201
Authoritarian Parenting							
6	Strong control procedures.	90 (50%)	30 (16.67%)	35 (19.44%)	25 (13.88%)	3.63	1.12
7	Requiring unwavering, rigorous compliance with parental authority.	70 (38.89%)	65 (36.11%)	15 (8.33%)	30 (16.67%)	3.57	0.07
8	Not ready to accept a child's uniqueness.	25 (13.88%)	15 (8.33%)	25 (13.88%)	115 (63.89%)	2.07	1.09
9	Parents who are harsh and punishing cope with disobedience.	15 (8.33%)	20 (11.11%)	20 (11.11%)	125 (69.44%)	1.90	0.98
10	Parent and child do not talk to one other much.	15 (8.33%)	15 (8.33%)	30 (16.67%)	120 (66.67%)	1.90	0.95
11	High-handed behavior.	5 (2.78%)	25 (13.88%)	40 (22.22%)	110 (61.11%)	1.90	0.82
Permissive Parenting							
12	Frequent warmth and compassion expression.	45 (25%)	20 (11.11%)	55 (30.56%)	60 (33.33%)	2.73	1.16
13	Low enforcement of rules and authority.	28 (15.55%)	42 (23.33%)	25 (13.88%)	85 (47.22%)	2.49	1.15
14	High approval.	30 (16.67%)	32 (17.78%)	26 (14.44%)	92 (51.11%)	2.40	1.164
15	Assuming the position of a friend as opposed to a parent.	15 (8.33%)	20 (11.11%)	45 (25%)	100 (55.56%)	2.07	0.96
16	Allow the youngster to decide for themselves.	15 (8.33%)	10 (5.56%)	35 (19.44%)	120 (66.67%)	1.87	0.92
17	minimal penalty	15 (8.33%)	25 (13.88%)	25 (13.88%)	115 (63.89%)	2.00	1.00
Negligent Parenting							
18	Unfocused behavior.	20 (11.11%)	10 (5.56%)	35 (19.44%)	115 (63.89%)	1.97	1.00
19	Abandoning the children.	15 (8.33%)	10 (5.56%)	75 (41.67%)	80 (44.44%)	2.13	0.88

20	Minimal contact with the youngster.	5 (2.78%)	20 (11.11%)	15 (8.33%)	140 (77.78%)	1.67	0.79
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ANT = Almost Never True; RT = Rarely True; ST = Sometimes True; AAT = Almost Always True

According to Table 2, the entire disclosures mean showed a moderate level. For Authoritative parenting style characterized by strong and reliable control (M = 2.20, SD = 0.93), 8.33% respondents almost never true, 11.11% rarely true, 65% sometimes true and 44.44% almost always true. For the statement expecting parents to keep an eye on their children' behavior and set clear expectations for it. (M = 2.40, SD = 1.15), 19.44% respondents almost never true, 8.33% rarely true, 25% sometimes true and 47.22% almost always true. For authoritarian parenting style for which parents who are harsh and punishing cope with disobedience (M = 1.90, SD = 0.98), 8.33% respondents almost never true, 11.11% rarely true, 11.11% sometimes true and 69.44% almost always true. "Parent and child don't talk to one other much" (M = 1.90, SD = 0.95), 8.33% respondents almost never true, 8.33% rarely true, 16.67% sometimes true and 66.67% almost always true. For permissive parenting style involving frequent warmth and compassion expression (M = 2.73, SD = 1.16), 25% respondents almost never true, 11.11% rarely true, 30.56% sometimes true and 33.33% almost always true. "Low enforcement of rules and authority." (M = 2.49, SD = 1.15), 15.55% respondents almost never true, 23.33% rarely true, 13.88% sometimes true and 47.22% almost always true. For negligent parenting style involving unfocused behavior (M = 1.97, SD = 1.00), 11.11% respondents almost never true, 5.56% rarely true, 19.44% sometimes true and 63.89% almost always true. The mean level of statements was in between 2.2 to 3.63. Items 5, 6, 7 and 12 have a mean score above 2.50 and were accepted with standard deviation of 1.201, 1.12 and 1.16 were accepted respectively. While item 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 having mean scores below 2.50 were rejected.

3.3. *Research question two: Do parenting styles affect the emotional adjustment of the secondary school students?*

Table 3: Correlation coefficient Matrix showing relationship between parenting styles and the emotional adjustment of the secondary school students

		Parenting Styles	Emotional Adjustment
Parenting Styles	Pearson Correlation	1	-.077
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.747
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	6.984	-.586
	Covariance	.368	-.031
Emotional Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	-.077	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.747	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	-.586	8.298
	Covariance	-.031	.437

In Table 3, parenting styles and emotional adjustment are correlated. The magnitude and direction of the linear relationship between the two variables are shown by these values. A perfect negative correlation would have a correlation coefficient of -1, a perfect positive correlation would have a correlation value of +1, and a correlation coefficient of zero would have no correlation at all (Lu, Jiang, Wan, Yin, Xu & Dai, 2022). Pearson A correlation value of -.077 indicates that there is little correlation between parenting styles and secondary school children's emotional adjustment. This implies that changes in one variable may not always correspond to changes in the other (Schober, Boer & Schwarte, 2018). Although perceived parenting styles and discipline are both linked to emotional adjustment, McKinney, Milone, and Renk (2011) argue that when combined with perceived discipline, perceived parenting styles are only linked to emotional adjustment for females.

Because of the negative correlation (-.077), greater values of one variable are related to lower values of the other. This finding is in line with earlier study by Sartaj and Aslam (2010), who found a negative link between authoritarian parenting style and emotional adjustment. The emotional adjustment of children was also shown to be negatively correlated with authoritarian and permissive parenting styles in a recent study by Boediman and Desnawati (2019). The study's conclusion is that there is no statistically significant relationship between parenting styles and secondary school students' emotional adjustment since the significance (2-Tailed) value of .747 is higher than .05. Jabeen, Anis-ul-Haque, and Riaz found a similar finding (2013) reported that neither the parenting style of the mother nor the father was important. Therefore, changes in parental behavior are not substantially correlated with changes in secondary school adolescents' emotional adjustment.

This research has several limitations. First off, self-statement measures, which may be subjective and skewed by social desirability, were used to collect the data for this study. In the future, data collection methods could include both self-report and assessments from third parties. Second, despite the study's theoretical underpinnings, prospective research is still required to fully understand the role that parenting styles play in the developing process of adolescents' emotional adjustment because it is challenging to identify deep causal relationships between variables using the research design that was chosen. Third, while this study looked at parenting styles, it did not differentiate between them. Additionally, past research has revealed that dads and mothers' parenting methods have varied impacts on their children (Dan-Ni, & Zhong-Beng, 2017). As a result, parenting practices might be looked at individually in future research. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that parental negotiations and interactions during child raising have a substantial impact on children's adjustment (Liu et al., 2021). Future studies should look at how parenting practices, particularly cooperative parenting practices, affect university students' social adjustment.

4. Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that parents of secondary school children in Nnewi South LGA of Anambra State tended to use authoritarian parenting more frequently than other parenting philosophies. Additionally, there is just a tenuous connection between parental parenting practices and secondary school students' emotional adjustment. This indicates that changes in parenting practices are not connected to changes in the emotional adjustment of teenagers. Additionally, there is no statistically significant link between parenting styles and secondary school children's emotional adjustment.

As a result, parents need to be careful about the parenting philosophies they choose. Due to the high degree of moral development among secondary school students in the Nnewi South LGA of Anambra State, school administrators and parents should take further steps to maintain this level. Additionally, the institution should devise activities for the school counselor to start a program that will assist secondary school students in developing a healthy self-concept and stable emotional adjustment.

Clarification is still required in many areas, despite the fact that parent-child interactions in general and parenting practices in particular have been the subject of much research over the last few decades. Our understanding of parenting methods has grown thanks to the current study, particularly as it relates to the generation of secondary school students in Nnewi South, Anambra State, Nigeria. Future studies in this area should take into account information from various rater viewpoints and examine the effects of the four main parenting approaches mentioned in the literature on children's academic achievement separately. The results of the current study would be strengthened and expanded if done so within the framework of a longitudinal design.

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Conflict of Interest

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: CPU. Sample collection: CPU, Formal analysis: CPU. Funding acquisition: CPU, Methodology: CPU, Data analysis: CPU, Writing – original draft, review & editing: CPU.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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